

[Jesse Pearson]

Could you introduce yourself? Who am I speaking to today?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

I'm an anesthesiologist, been an anesthesiologist for 14 years in West Caldwell, New Jersey.

Before going to medical school though, I majored in history at Brandeis.

[Jesse Pearson]

Now I'm wondering if you can tell me a little about vaccine use and its history in the United States?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

Well, vaccine use in the United States goes as far back as the Revolutionary War period, when George Washington inoculated his troops against smallpox. It's actually pretty gross how they figured out this initial vaccine. They figured out the smallpox vaccine by taking a cowpox pustule and injecting it into certain troops. From doing this, they noticed that the troops who got injected were much less likely to develop smallpox. This worked because the body learned how to fight against the cowpox injected and remembered that technique in order to more effectively fight off smallpox. In the last 120–150 years, though, as people have recognized certain bacteria as causes of predictable illnesses, they've found more enhanced methods of inoculation that can now be widespread.

[Jesse Pearson]

Now, I do want to get into how you think the vaccine movement has changed over the last 10-20 years?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

Well, I can't talk about how it's changed within the last 10–20 years without mentioning how it really began about 25 years ago. In 1997 or 1998, there was a paper published in *The Lancet*¹ by a guy named Andrew Wakefield. The paper pretty much created a link between the MMR vaccine, which most children get to prevent measles, mumps, and rubella, and the development of autism. The paper ended up being retracted, but the damage was still done. The press got a hold of it, Oprah got a hold of it, and it all just got blown up. It's sad, too, because I understand why people initially believed it. People saw that there are many more vaccines to get nowadays and that there seem to be many more individuals with autism nowadays, and so the correlation between the two does make sense. I mean, I wish the cause of autism was just as simple as the injection of a vaccine, but this study was just a case of correlation not being equal to causation.

[Jesse Pearson]

I understand that.

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

I mean, you might've heard this comparison before, but the rise in autism can even be compared to the rise in left-handed individuals. In the early 1900s, it was taboo to be left-handed. My dad actually thinks he was born left-handed and that his parents forced him to write with his right hand. Fast forward to the 1960s, and nobody gave a f*ck anymore about whether or not someone

¹ *The Lancet* is a peer-reviewed medical journal that publishes research, reviews, and commentary on global health and clinical medicine.

was right or left-handed. This led to a temporary rise in left-handed individuals that eventually leveled off. With autism, the definitions have changed over the years. We're much more adept at recognizing when people have autism, and it isn't as taboo as it once was, so there's an increase in the number of individuals diagnosed with it. It's still the case, though, that the number of individuals diagnosed with autism will eventually level off, because there isn't a direct cause for autism—just like there isn't a direct cause for left-handedness.

[Jesse Pearson]

Keeping this in mind, How did you see the anti-vax movement change with the introduction of the Covid-19 vaccine?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

It became politicized with Covid, and that's an issue people keep running into now when trying to discuss vaccines. Many people don't know the science of vaccines, so talking about the politics of them is much easier to manage. Have you ever heard of the Dunning–Kruger effect?

[Jesse Pearson]

No, do you mind explaining it?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

It's an effect where, when you first learn a little bit about a subject, you think you know a lot about that subject, but when you keep learning more, you realize how much you don't know. So, on social media, it's easy for many people to know about the politics surrounding vaccines, and that's why so many people talk about them. If they learned a little more about the science behind vaccines, though, they would realize how little they really know about the topic as a whole. I think poor education is also to blame—I mean, people just don't know, and they're scared of what they don't know.

[Jesse Pearson]

Yeah, I think that fear is definitely a big factor in why people do or don't get vaccines.

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

100%, and you know, some of it is the way we put stuff out there in the media—like, anytime you see an advertisement for a vaccine, you get the image of this giant, scary needle! No wonder so many people, children included, are initially hesitant.

[Jesse Pearson] Yeah that's a good point.

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

Also, the anti-vax movement created with the Covid vaccine bled into anti-vax movements toward other vaccines. Because of the anti-vax movement, we're seeing resurgent rates of measles, when back in 2000, measles was considered eradicated. It's scary because measles is

one of the most infectious organisms known to man. If someone with measles walks through a room, it could be hours to days before someone else walks through that same room and catches measles from that person. It's so infectious that you need up to 95% of the population to be vaccinated in order to prevent outbreaks. As soon as that drops below 95%, it's going to propagate again—and it has recently, because we're below 90% now in this country. The 2019 measles outbreak in Samoa should've served as an example to the United States, as there were around 6,000 cases and 83 people dead!

[Jesse Pearson]

I didn't know that. I mean I never thought about that even being an issue anymore.

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

Right, well, like I said, that 1998 paper did a lot of damage regarding the MMR vaccine and vaccines in general. Covid's only made it worse since then. I mean, it's been like 27 years since that article, but the effects are still being felt.

[Jesse Pearson]

So this kind of brings me back to a question that we touched on, but how do you think social media has played a role in the anti-vax movement?

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

So, I mean, if Covid had hit, say, in the 1980s—right?—there's no internet, there's no social media, there are four channels on TV, and everyone tunes in to watch Dan Rather² at the end of

² The *Dan Rather Evening News* was a nightly CBS news program (1981–2005) known for its serious, fact-driven reporting on national and international events, anchored by journalist Dan Rather.

the night. Is that a more effective way to get the message out about the importance or the science behind getting vaccinated? Maybe, because everyone's just watching the same thing rather than formulating public opinions on it. I feel like nowadays, anyone can find any information that confirms what they want to hear. It's confirmation bias. Like, if you're a person who is an anti-vaxxer, you're more likely to consume media that is anti-vax oriented, and your algorithm knows this. That type of freedom to get confirmation on any type of suspicion didn't exist just 45 years ago, and that's why we have movements such as the anti-vax one today.

Social media is just much more black and white than a lot of people realize, and it doesn't allow for people to deeply discuss the risks versus rewards. Social media is structured into quick comments without a lot of true back-and-forth weighing of a situation. Everything we do as doctors has risks. Even giving somebody supplemental oxygen³ has risks—very low risks—but there are risks and benefits to everything we do in medicine. Part of our decision-making when we're choosing therapies and vaccines for patients is balancing those risks versus benefits. For example, in some people, the Covid vaccine can cause myocarditis, a little inflammation around the heart. It'll usually go away within a couple of weeks, but the problem is, in today's world where people can share media, one person's bad reaction can get blown up and give thousands of people who aren't even susceptible to cardiac myocarditis a reason not to take the shot.

[Jesse Pearson]

Now I'm curious how you see the anti-vax movement heading in the future? Do you think it is more of a just topical issue depending on what viruses are out there at the moment?

³ The act of providing extra oxygen to individuals whose bodies aren't getting enough oxygen on their own, typically due to a medical condition

[Dr. Joshua Rubin]

I don't think it was ever a topical issue. I think we're in real trouble. I mean, two weeks ago, all 17 members of the ACIP⁴ were removed, and it was disbanded from the CDC⁵. We've already seen decreases in childhood vaccination, and I'm worried that this is only the beginning.

⁴ The Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP) is a panel of medical and public health experts that develops recommendations on vaccine use to protect public health in the United States.

⁵ The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) is a U.S. federal agency that works to protect public health by monitoring diseases, promoting prevention, and responding to health threats.